

Is Math Really Tough?

May Rose A. Espia - Macrohon, PhD

Assistant Professor III/South Cotabato State College

Numbers and symbols can be confusing, and formulas so difficult to remember,
Problems are overwhelming, like a great wall you can't even climb over.
Does every Math challenge really have a lesson to offer?
This question, as a teacher, I always encounter.

Dear students, making mistakes is not the end,
When you fail, embrace the chance to do it again.
With courage and persistence, you will grow.
You'll see the purpose of Math for all you know.

Teachers keep working hard and are always hopeful,
That someday their students will be grateful.
Knowing that numbers and symbols in life are helpful,
And that Math can help brighten their future.

Even though exams can be really stressful,
Just do it and work hard, and it'll pay you in full.
The look of numbers can sometimes be really scary.
But the courage in you will make it a little less dreary.

Dream big with Math, let your spirit arise,
Accept every challenge, be bold, and be wise.
In every equation solved, celebrate with a blast.
With persistence and trust, success will come at last.

Math is not really Tough!

DOI 10.5281/zenodo.20917331

*Copyright & Published in the Philippines ©2026
by Pinagpala Publishing Services*